
Analysis of Rice Husk Ash for a Renewable Raw Material to Blend/Replace Limestone for the Production of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC)

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Abstract

The production of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) from rice husk was carried out using the laboratory scaled muffle furnace. The ash was analysed and found to have the oxides of Si, Al, Fe, Ca, Mg, K, Na, S and Loss on ignition and absence of free lime. All these oxides are in the Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) too, but with the presence of free lime. SiO₂, one of the most important components in cement is observed to be higher in RHA than in OPC. CaO that gives rise to calcium carbide, which provides the strength of cement is lower in RHA. Aluminium oxide, which is C₃A in cement fall short of the standard, though higher aluminium value in cement brings construction problems. Iron oxide, which is higher in OPC may have come from the addition of laterite. Magnesium oxide also slightly falls short of the standard, but too much of it causes unsoundness. Potassium oxide is seen to be higher in RHA. Too much of it attacks kiln and concretes. OPC shows higher amount of sulphate which might have come from gypsum. Loss on ignition which is the test of impurities when a material is ignited is appropriate in the RHA. Free lime is the excess of uncombined lime in cement. This is not present in RHA, higher volume causes unsoundness in cement. A blend of certain ratios of RHA and OPC was used and moulded solid sandcrete blocks to confirm their suitability for block making and other constructions works. A 12 × 25cm solid sandcrete blocks were cast, cured and crushed for 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9 days at 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50% blended. The compressive strength of OPC/RHA sandcrete blocks increases at age on curing of 16.00, 25.50, 26.00, 28.00, 32.00N/mm²; 6.00, 10.40, 14.20, 18.60, 20.50N/mm²; 4.20, 8.50, 12.10, 16.30, 18.40N/mm²; 2.00, 6.00, 9.30, 14.40, 16.70N/mm²; 0.80, 4.20, 7.20, 9.20, 10.50,N/mm² corresponding with 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50% replacement levels. This decreased as the percentage of RHA content increases. The soundness of block samples for various blending levels was 0.50, 0.45, 0.30, 0.25, 0.20, 0.15cm respectively. The initial and final setting time of the various blends are 121, 142, 153, 162, 201, 273minutes; 183, 232, 185, 281, 352, 394minutes in that order. The result indicates that 20% of RHA can optimally be blended with 80% OPC as showed by the time of setting.

Key Words: RHA, OPC, Setting time, Soundness, Curing, Blending

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Introduction

In 2005, Krishnarao and Godkhindi estimated the quantity of rice husk produced yearly to stand at 596.5 million tons; this volume is undoubtedly increasing as the population increases. Rice husk is the shell that covers the rice grain which consists of two interlocking halves. As is it non-edible, it is always peeled from the rice grain by either hand threshing or using a machine. Hence, rice husk is a direct by-product of rice. The rice husk can be transformed into other important products such as sodium silicate, activated carbon, furfural, silicon nitrate, silicon carbide and so on (Govindaro, 2000 and Bakar *et al.*, 2010).

Chopra *et al.*, (2001) estimated that the content of rice in the husk ranges between 16.3 – 26 wt. % but generally 20 wt. % is considered to be an acceptable average value. The husk on combustion yields Rice Husk Ash (RHA) which amounts to about 20 wt. % of the husk (Kapur, 2001; Kassim and Chern, 2004). However, 23.9 million tons of rice husk ash (RHA) as a renewable source of silicious material is potentially available worldwide. Due to the high silica content in rice, the ash obtained may be over 95 wt. % when completely burnt (Krishnarao and Godkhindi, 2005).

Rice husk consists of two parts: (i) Organic matter (ii) Inorganic mineral matter. The organic matter consists of cellulose, lignin, pentosans and small amount of proteins and vitamins, while the main component of the inorganic mineral matter is silica. The silicon present in the rice husk is distributed in the organic material of the husk at the molecular level. This silicon exists in a hydrated amorphous form of silica, probably biogenetic opal or silica gel (Lanning, 2002 and Ibrahim and El-Hemaly, 2003).

The bid to lower down the high cost of Ordinary Portland Cement in order to afford accommodation and good roads for the society has intensified research into the use of some locally available renewable materials that could be used as partial or replacement of limestone for the production of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) in civil engineering and other construction works. Supplementary cementation materials have proven to be effective in meeting most of the requirements of durable concrete bricks and blended cements are now used in many parts of the world (Krishnarao and Godkhindi, 2005).

Over the years, cement has been the main material used for stabilization or improving the engineering properties of soil. However, the cost of this material has rapidly

skyrocketed due to the sharp increase in the cost of energy. The limestone and/or marble deposits used in the production of cement are fast depleting and can never be

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replaced and at the same time, the mining activities of these substances are seriously devastating the environment. Thus, the use of agricultural waste such as Rice Husk Ash (RHA) in house, road and bridge construction will considerably reduce the cost of construction and as well reduce the environmental hazards caused by mountains of rice husk and the environmental devastation experienced by the mining activities of the limestone and marble.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to analyse the chemical composition of rice husk, produce ash from it to mould a block for comparison with that produced from Ordinary Portland Cement. This aim will be achieved by the following objectives:

- (i) The combustion of rice husk using muffle furnace at a temperature between 600 and 800°C.
- (ii) The determination of chemical components of the combusted ash and ordinary Portland cement.
- (iii) The comparison of the physical properties such as fineness and soundness of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) and Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC).
- (iv) Comparison of the physical properties such as compressive strength and setting time of the molded bricks from both RHA and OPC

Literature Review

Many different research works have been carried out on the blends of Ordinary Portland Cement with different pozzolans in making cement. Rice Husk Ash (RHA) which is an agricultural by-product was suggested to be a good pozzolan by numerous researchers. Mehta and Polivka (2005) investigated the use of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) to reducing temperature in high strength mass concrete and got result showing that RHA is very effective in reducing the temperature of mass concrete compared to OPC concrete. Mansarary and Ghaly (2007) later reported that ground RHA with finer particle size than OPC improves concrete properties, including that higher substitution results in lower water absorption values and the addition of rice husk causes an increment in the compressive strength. Cordeiro *et al.* (2009) carried out studies of Brazilian RHA and Rice Straw Ash (RSA) and demonstrated that grinding increases the pozzolanicity of RHA and that high strength of RHA make production of bricks with good bearing strength possible. Their study showed that the combination of RHA with

lime produces a weak cementation material. Habeeb and Fayyadh (2009) investigated the influence of RHA average particle size on the properties of concrete and found out

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that at early stages of 28 days, finer RHA exhibited higher strength than the sample with coarse RHA. Rukzon *et al.* (2009) further studied the effect of grinding on the chemical and physical properties of Rice Husk Ash and the effect of RHA fineness on properties of mortar and found that pozzolans with finer particles had greater pozzolanic reaction.

In addition, Sear (2005) reported that by the nature of limestone chemistry, Portland cement produces large quantities of carbon dioxide (CO₂) for every ton of its final product. Therefore, replacing proportion of the Portland cement in soil stabilization with a secondary cementitious material such as RHA will not only reduce the cost of construction but also reduce the overall environmental impact of the stabilization process.

Chemical Composition of Rice Husk Ash

The chemical analysis of the ash obtained by complete burning of rice husk revealed silica as the main component, minor quantity of alkalis and trace elements. The presence of silica in RHA is reported to be in the range between 94% and 96% (Houston, 2002; James and Rao., 2006; Hannah and Farag, 2005). The main impurity of ash is formed by alkalis of which potassium is the predominant constituent. The rice husk ash of America and Spain has potassium contents of about 0.18% to 3.4%, while sodium content is less than 0.1%; Phosphorus, iron and magnesium are negligible (Singh *et al.*, 2005; Houston, 2002).

Table 1: Chemical Properties of Rice Husk Ash

S/N	Particular	Formula	Proportion (%)
1	Silicon dioxide	SiO ₂	86.94
2	Aluminium oxide	Al ₂ O ₃	0.2
3	Iron Oxide	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.1
4	Calcium oxide	CaO	0.3-2.2
5	Sodium oxide	Na ₂ O	0.1-0.8
6	Potassium oxide	K ₂ O	2.15-2.30
7	Magnesium oxide	MgO	0.2-0.6
8	Loss on Ignition	-	3.15-4.4

Source: Bui and Stroeven, (2009)

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Pozzolanic Reaction Mechanism

When a pozzolanic reacts with calcium hydroxide in the presence of humidity it forms a compound with cementitious properties (Papadakis and Tsimas, 2002). Omotosoa *et al.* (2005) opined that for a hydrate of cement to develop, the calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) and calcium hydroxide $\{Ca(OH)_2\}$ or (CH) are released within the hydration of two main components of cement giving dicalcium silicate (C_2S) or $2CaO.SiO_2$ and tricalcium silicate (C_3S) or $3CaO.SiO_2$ where C and S represent CaO and SiO_2 respectively. Hydration of C_2S , C_3S also C_3A and C_4AF (where A and F denote Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 in that order) is very important. Upon hydration, the following reactions occur;

The C-S-H gets generated by the hydration of C_2S and C_3S in the first two equations which is the main strengthening constituents. Calcium hydroxide $[Ca(OH)_2]$ and $3CaO.3CaSO_4.31H_2O$ that are crystalline hydration products are randomly distributed and form the frame of gel-like products. Hydration of C_4AF consumes calcium hydroxide $Ca(OH)_2$ and generates gel-like products. Excess $Ca(OH)_2$ can be detrimental to concrete strength due to tending the crystalline growth in one direction (Papadakis and Tsimas, 2002).

Temperature Effects

Exothermal reaction occurs during the cement hydration and hydration heat is an essential aspect that influences the setting and characteristics behaviour of Portland cements. This temperature variation from the initial moment of setting until the hardening of cement may cause shrinkage which may result in the cracks formation that can be seen in some construction (Rojas *et al.*, 2003). Cement blended with pozzolanic materials usually has decreased heat of hydration compared to pure cement during the period of C_3S ($3CaO.SiO_2$) hydration (Mustafa and Brown, 2005). Pozzolanic material mainly depends on three factors, C_3S hydration, aluminate hydration and pozzolanic reaction (Hewlet, 2008).

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC)

This is the most used cement and is suitable for most types of work. It has a medium rate of setting and hardening. Ordinary Portland Cement is one of the several types of cement being manufactured throughout the world, OPC is general purpose cement

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used in concrete construction. Sumrereng *et al.* (2009) reported that OPC is a compound composed of lime (CaO), silica (SiO₂), Alumina (Al₂O₃), Iron (Fe₂O₃) and Sulphur Trioxide (SO₃), Magnesium (MgO) is present in small quantities as impurities associated with limestone. SO₃ is added at the grinding stage to retard the setting time of the finished cement.

Portland Blast Furnace Cement (PBFC)

This is obtained by grinding OPC clinker with 30 -70% blast furnace slag, a waste product in the manufacture of pig iron, has the same components as OPC except for a lower CaO (Nhedi *et al.*, 2008).

Table 2: The Composition of Portland Cement

Component	Chemical Formula	Abbreviation
Tricalcium silicate	3CaO.SiO ₃	C ₃ S
Dicalcium silicate	2CaO.SiO ₂	C ₂ S
Tricalcium aluminate	3CaO.Al ₂ O ₃	C ₃ A
Tetracalciumalumino ferrite	4CaO.Al ₂ O ₃ .Fe ₂ O ₃	C ₄ AF

Source: Bui and Stroeven, (2009)

Table 3: Typical Percent Components of Portland Cement

Cement	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O/K ₂ O	SO ₃	TiO	Mn ₂ O ₃	Loss on Ignition
OPC	64.78	21.31	8.08	2.77	0.88	0.91	1.01	0.33	0.11	2.27
RHPC	64.30	20.82	5.25	3.01	1.13	0.96	2.01	0.35	0.7	0.94
LHPC	61.00	25.44	4.57	2.07	1.64	0.90	2.22	0.24	0.08	2.10
SRPC	62.40	21.15	4.03	5.63	0.88	0.88	2.86	0.28	0.12	0.96

Source: Villar-Cocin *et al.* (2003)

OPC = Ordinary Portland Cement, RHPC = Rapid Hardening Portland Cement

LHPC = Low-Heat Portland Cement, SRPC = SuperRapid Portland Cement

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Research Methodology

Carbonization of Rice Husk

There are several methods for converting rice husks to ash; the simplest way is to burn rice husk in open air, which is open heap up burning. Sugita (2003) produced Rice Husk Ash in a boiler furnace which used rice husk as a fuel for producing steam. Malhotra and Mehta (2004) used the cyclone-type furnace which utilized the heat value of husk and to produce ashes with high reactivity. In this experiment, a muffle furnace was employed where amorphous ashes with high pozzolanic activity may be produced.

Sample Collection

The rice husk was collected from Fan in Fan district of BarkinLadi Local Government Area of Plateau State. The husk was found stock piled into three different hips as a result of threshing of parboiled rice, the separation of seed or grain from its outer covering or husk in a small scaled domestic rice mill. Seven shovels full from each of the hips was scooped, thoroughly mixed to ensure homogeneous distribution of husk and then finally re-bagged.

Equipment and Materials

The equipment utilized in both the production of the RHA and bricks of different percentages of RHA/OPC include: spatula, test tube, electric LabMan MAB 220 weighing balance, PlusFurnace (500 - 1400°C) muffle furnace, porcelain crucible, filter paper, conical flask, SpectroLab SLE-S-935 flame photometer, pipette, glass funnel, flue chamber, sieve, wooden mould and hand trowel. Others include; head pan, Gilson LR100K compressive strength machine, soundness test machine/soundness mould, shovel, graduated cylinder, Vicatt's apparatus, needle and hard rubber ring. The materials consist of rice husk, rice husk ash, OPC and sand while the reagents were conc. H_2SO_4 , conc. HNO_3 , H_2O_2 , distilled water and saline water.

Washing and Drying of Rice Husk

Rice-husk obtained from a rice mill was washed to remove sand and stones contaminants. The washed rice husks were then sprayed on a plastic tray, materials like the broken rice grain were removed by hand picking and local air floating. The husk was dried at 100°C in an electric oven.

Carbonization of Rice Husk Using Furnace

The muffle furnace is a laboratory-scaled type of furnace which can take a little more than 500g of rice husk at a time. The rice husk was placed in a protective pan that prevented the material from coming in contact with direct heat and also prevented the material from pouring into the furnace. It was then placed into the furnace and converted to reactive amorphous ash under a controlled temperature of between 680 - 800°C for one hour and moisture-free environment. The furnace was set to stop automatically at exactly one hour of each batch and the ash was allowed to cool before collection. This batch-wise procedure was continued until 4kg of rice husk was ashed. The furnace stopped automatically at exactly one hour of each batch as timed and the ash was allowed to cool before collection.

The 500g each of the rice husk produced 350g of reactive amorphous ash, implying that the total amount of the ash produced from 4kg of husk was 2.8kg and the total time taken at a constant temperature between 680 and 800°C was eight (8) hours.

Ash Digestion and Analysis of Rice Husk Ash (RHA)

Two grams of RHA was fetched into a test tube using spatula and divided into two. Specimen A was dissolved in 50ml of distilled water, 7ml of concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3)_(aq), 2 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid H_2SO_4 _(aq) and 2ml of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). This specimen was called the digest. The specimen was also split into two: specimen A₁ and specimen A₂. Specimen A₁ was dissolved in 50ml of distilled water and specimen A₂ dissolved in 50ml of saline water both which were termed blank specimens. All of these samples were allowed for 3 hours to ensure homogeneous digestion after when they were filtered by the use of filter paper, glass funnel, and conical flask. The filtrate was collected in a test tube and analysed with a flame photometer. The blank specimens were analysed with flame photometer and dictated the presence of oxides of magnesium, aluminium, silicon, sulphur, iron, potassium, calcium and sodium.

Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrophotometry (EDXRFS)

Energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrophotometry is a quantitative X-ray micro analytical technique that provides information on a chemical composition of a sample.

An electron beam was focused on the sample in a Transmission Electron Detector (TEM). The electrons from the primary beam penetrated the sample and interacted with the atoms from which the sample was made. Two types of X-ray results were expected from this: the background and the characteristic X-rays. The X-rays were detected by an

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energy dispersive analyser which displayed the signal as a spectrum of intensity (number of X-rays) vs X-ray energy. The energies of the characteristic X-rays allowed the elements making up the sample to be identified, while the intensities of the characteristics X-rays allowed the concentration of the elements to be quantified. The SkyrayEDX36000H EDXRF was used.

Moulding Process of Blocks

Seven solid blocks were moulded from the mixture; 2,698g of reddish-brown sand, 1,200ml of water and different percent replacement level of cement with RHA. The first block was made from a mortar of 400g of 100% OPC; the second, 10 wt.% blend of RHA. The same procedure was repeated for 20%, 30%, 40%, 50% and 100% blending/replacement of RHA maintaining the same volume of sand and water. The blocks were allowed to dry under the sun for 3 days.

Curing of Specimen

The moulded bricks were submerged in a chamber containing a reasonable volume of clean water at room temperature and cured for a period of 9 days before hydration test and crushing.

Test for Hydration

The weight of the dry specimen was measured and recorded first before submerging it in water and their weights were measured at an interval of two days; 1st, 3rd, 5th, 7th and 9th day on immersion in water.

$$\text{Level of hydration (g)} = \text{Wet Weight} - \text{Dry Weight of Specimen}$$

Burning of Specimen

The specimens were burned or heated in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 150°C to expel the mechanically bound waters.

Crushing of Sample

The solid block samples were crushed using hydraulic press. This was done by placing the specimen on a moveable steel block stand which moved the sample upward and

crushed it against the top steel block of the machine as a result of hydraulic hand pumping. Readings were taken immediately when the hydraulic pump resisted pumping for the first, third, fifth, seventh and finally the 9th day. Each sample was completely crushed and the compressive strength recorded.

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Soundness Test

Fragments from each of the crushed specimen (solid block) were collected and mixed with water. Each of these mixtures for the different specimen was fetched into a mould placed on a piece of plane glass slab. The mould has two dictating sticks from which the readings of the expansion were taken by measuring the length between the mid-points of the sticks. Reading before heating was taken and recorded after which the sticks on the soundness mould were fastened together with a thread. The soundness samples were covered both at the top and bottom of the mould and submerged in water in soundness tank. The moulds were heated for three hours and allowed to cool and the readings after heating or final readings were taken and recorded appropriately.

$$\text{Expansion} = \text{Reading before heating} - \text{Reading after heating}$$

Initial Setting Time

A needle of 1mm diameter was set on the lower end of the movable rod and released for 30 seconds and the time of release was noted and recorded along with the penetration of the needle in the paste. After a period of time, the needle was again released and the releasing time recorded along with the penetration of the needle in the paste. The above step was repeated until the penetration became 25mm which is the ASTM standard. The total time was calculated up to this step which was the initial setting time.

Final Setting Time

A needle of 5mm diameter was set on the lower end of the rod and released for 30 seconds, and the time of release was recorded. The steps were repeated until the needle could no longer penetrate the paste or left an impression. The procedure was carried out using the time of release intervals of 30 seconds, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, and 3.5 minutes, for 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50% replacement levels respectively.

Results

Chemical Analysis from Flame Photometer

Table 4: Qualitative Chemical Analysis of Rice Husk Ash

Element Detected	Blank Sample (A) in parameter power (P)		Digested Specimen (in parameter power (P))
	A ₁	A ₂	
RHA	A ₁	A ₂	B
Si	0.27	0.14	0.35
Al	0.18	0.35	0.59
Fe	0.44	0.59	0.42
Ca	0.26	0.19	0.28
Mg	0.17	0.74	0.24
K	0.18	0.29	0.45
Na	0.21	0.19	0.50
S	0.13	0.29	0.48

Table 5: Quantitative Chemical Analysis of Rice Husk Ash and OPC

S/N	Constituent	(Determined) RHA (wt. %)	(Standard) OPC (wt. %)
1	SiO ₂	90.04	23.33
2	CaO	1.25	62.05
3	Al ₂ O ₃	0.30	3.73
4	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.44	3.08
5	MgO	1.25	1.35
6	K ₂ O	1.40	0.29
7	Na ₂ O	0.09	0.18
8	SO ₃	0.01	1.10
9	LOI (Lost on Ignition)	4.51	0 -12
10	Free lime	-	1.5

From Table 5, the SiO₂ content is one of the most important constituents of cement. The silica content of the RHA was found to be 90.04% which indicates higher silica content than in OPC.

Calcium carbide is responsible for the formation of C₃S (3CaO.SiO₂) in cement and is responsible for the strength in late or early part of concrete or mortar.

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In the presence of RHA that contains 60% and above the SiO₂ will combine with released calcium hydrate, CaO.H₂O{Ca(OH)}.

This means that Ca(OH)₂ is being depleted from the system. The percentage CaO in RHA was 1.25% much lower than that in Portland cement (62.05%).

Alumina content is lower in RHA than OPC sample. Higher alumina in cement in form of C₃A(3CaO.Al₂O₃) will lead to widespread construction problems due to its faster hardening properties (Hewlett, 1998). On the other hand, the percentage of Iron (ii) oxide (Fe₂O₃) in RHA is 0.44% much lower than that of OPC (3.08%). The iron (ii) oxide in the OPC may arise from the laterite associated with the geological formation. Higher amount of Fe₂O₃ is responsible for impacting colour.

Similarly, low magnesia was obtained in RHA falling below the standard of 1.35%. Higher magnesia content is not required in cement because it causes unsoundness. Potassium oxide (K₂O) is the main alkali constituent associated with cement, there is high percentage of it in RHA than in OPC. Higher percentage of alkali in cement is not needed as it causes damage to kiln and attack concretes and mortar. Higher sulphate content in OPC could be from gypsum (CaSO₄.2H₂O) which is one of the raw materials in cement used in controlling setting time. Cement products with higher amount of sulphate are acid resistant. Loss on ignition obtained is equal to 4.51 wt. % which falls within the expected standard of 0 -12% maximum for pozzolans. Higher loss on the ignition above 12% is an indication of prehydration and combustion which may be due to improper and prolong storage and adulteration during transportation or transfer. Free lime content is the excess of uncombined lime in cement. The RHA is observed not to have free lime. Higher amount of free lime is undesirable as it is the main cause of unsoundness in hydrated cement, thus, responsible for cracking in concrete.

Mixing Proportion of Block Samples

Table 6: Mixture Used in Making Mortar for Block Moulding

OPC (%)	RHA (%)	OPC (g)	RHA (g)	Sand (g)	Water/Binder (ml/g)
100.00	0.00	400.00	0.00	2,698.00	3.00
90.00	10.00	360.00	40.00	2,698.00	3.00
80.00	20.00	320.00	80.00	2,698.00	3.00
70.00	30.00	280.00	120.00	2,698.00	3.00

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60.00	40.00	240.00	160.00	2,698.00	3.00
50.00	50.00	200.00	200.00	2,698.00	3.00
0.00	100.00	0.00	400.00	2,698.00	3.00

RHA: Rice Husk Ash; OPC: Ordinary Portland Cement

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Effects of Cement Replacement on the Soundness of Block

Table 7: Result on Soundness of Cement Replacement

OPC (Wt. %)	RHA (Wt. %)	Before Heating (cm)	After Heating (cm)	Soundness
100.00	0.00	1.40	1.90	0.50
90.00	10.00	1.45	1.90	0.45
80.00	20.00	1.50	1.80	0.30
70.00	30.00	1.50	1.75	0.25
60.00	40.00	1.40	1.60	0.20
50.00	50.00	1.40	1.55	0.15

Table 7 shows decrease in expansion as the percentage replacement of OPC with RHA increases. The expansion or unsoundness of cement is due to the amount of free lime as seen in Table 5.

Ten weight percent OPC replacement with RHA has an expansion of 0.45cm less than 0wt. % replacement with RHA giving 0.50cm. The expansion keeps on decreasing with increase in percentage of RHA. This is because the silica in ash substitutes some amount of the free lime initially present in OPC, this lead to decrease in the cracks of concrete.

Effects of Curing of Specimens on Compressive Strength and Hydration

Table 8: Compressive Strength and Hydration Results of Solid Sandcrete Blocks

OPC (Wt. %)	RHA (Wt. %)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)					Amount of Hydration in mix				
		1day	3days	5days	7days	9days	1day	3days	5days	7days	9days
100	0	16.00	25.50	26.00	28.00	32.00	2.00	3.50	4.00	4.20	4.50
90	10	12.60	14.00	18.00	22.00	26.00	2.20	3.80	4.50	5.00	5.50
80	20	6.00	10.40	14.20	18.60	20.50	2.60	4.00	4.70	5.30	5.80
70	30	4.20	8.50	12.10	16.30	18.40	3.00	4.50	4.90	5.60	6.00
60	40	2.00	6.00	9.30	14.40	16.70	3.40	4.80	5.20	6.00	7.50

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50	50	0.80	4.20	7.20	9.20	10.50	4.00	7.00	8.00	8.40	9.00
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Effects of Curing on Compressive Strength of Blocks

From Table 8, it is obvious that compressive strength of cement decreases with increase in the replacement level of cement with RHA. This indicates that the design strength of the specimens differs indirectly as the amount of RHA, but going day by day, the design strength of the block increases as the age of curing extends further. This implies that the design strength of block varies directly proportional to the age or time it spent in water.

Effects of Hydration on Curing

The rate of hydration of block increases as the weight percentage replacement increases.
Rate of hydration = Percentage weight of RHA × Age

Effects of Cement Replacement on Setting Time at Various Replacement Levels

Table 9: Results of setting time at Various Cement Replacement Levels

Mixing Ratio		Setting Time (minutes)	
OPC (wt. %)	RHA (wt. %)	Initial	Final
100.00	0.00	121.00	183.00
90.00	10.00	142.00	232.00
80.00	20.00	153.00	185.00
70.00	30.00	162.00	281.00
60.00	40.00	201.00	352.00
50.00	50.00	273.00	394.00

The initial - final setting times increase with increase in Rice Husk Ash (RHA) content. The reaction between water and cement is exothermic. According to Bakar *et al.* (2010), the liberation of heat and evaporation of moisture causes the hardening of the paste and slower heat induced evaporation of water from the OPC/RHA due to lower cement content. Therefore, an accelerated increase in the initial setting time of the mixture was observed as the percentage of RHA in the paste increased. Thus, an increase in the setting time was noticed from 142 minutes at 10wt. % RHA to 153 minutes at 20wt. % increment of RHA to the final level of replacement.

Conclusion

During the production of OPC using limestone, carbon monoxide is produced and causes greenhouse effect and environmental pollution such as global warming, acid rain. Due to the low amount or absence of carbon monoxide and other related compounds as a result of the production of a binder from rice husk ash and low energy consumption compared to the production of cement from limestone. RHA is a better replacement material for cement in block making.

Replacement of OPC with RHA reduces the rate at which the block is attacked by the sulphate ions. This is because most of the calcium oxide in OPC is replaced with silica in RHA which is less reactive to sulphate compounds. The expansion values which cause cracks in blocks decrease with increase in the replacement of RHA due to their absence of free lime. The compressive strength of all the block specimens increases with age at curing and decrease as the RHA content increases. It was obvious that the setting time of OPC/RHA paste increases as the RHA content increases which can improve the hardening of block. Therefore, due to high cost of mining limestone, rice husk is available in very large quantities as a waste and can be utilized for the production of a binder for making concrete blocks and a means of reducing waste from our environment.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are drawn:

- i. The study of other admixtures can be incorporated with rice husk ash in order to retard hydration of water.
- ii. Used of other raw materials such as gypsum could be added to improve the setting time of rice husk ash.
- iii. For further research, grinding and fineness test of RHA should be studied as to improve its binding effects.

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